

PROCESSING AND STORAGE STUDIES OF SQUASH PREPARED FROM MANGO (*Mangifera indica* L.) PULP AND *Moringa oleifera*'s LEAVES POWDER BLEND.Joshi Nirav. D^{1*}, Chudhari Viraj², A, Thakar Meetkumar³¹ Assistant Professor, College of Food Technology, S.D. Agricultural University, Sardarkrushinagar - 385 506, Dantiwada, Dist. Banaskantha (Gujarat)*Corresponding author's niravjoshi56@sdau.edu.in² Assistant Professor, Government Science College Vankal, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Ta. Mangrol, dist. Surat – 394430, email id: virajchaudhari2@gmail.com³ Ph.D .scholar, department of applied chemistry, faculty of technology and engineering The Maharaja Sayajirao University of baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat-390002,; meetthakar7296@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study was conducted with objective that utilizes therapeutic value of mango and drumstick leaves. In developed functional squash, on the basis of filler trial fixed quantity of mango pulp as 50 %, citric acid 0.5 %, ginger juice 01 %, Jaljira 01 %, and optimize sugar level as 25% & *Moringa oleifera*'s leaves powder now onwards it known as (MLP) 0.65% based on RSM. Add remaining quantity of water for make up 100 ml. Data were analyzed using the software, design expert, version 11.0.3.0 and Completely Randomized Design. Optimized functional squash were stored at refrigeration temperature ($5\pm 10^{\circ}\text{C}$) and ambient temperature ($26\pm 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) for a period of 4 weeks and quality parameters were assessed. The samples were coded as S_1 (stored at refrigeration temperature, $5\pm 10^{\circ}\text{C}$) & S_2 (stored at room temperature, $26\pm 30^{\circ}\text{C}$). It is also observed that there is very negligible variation in chemical properties (i.e. acidity and pH) and microbiological properties (TPC, Coliform count and TMC) during 28 days storage study. Sample S_1 is acceptable up to 4 week concern with quality and overall acceptance while for same Sample S_2 is acceptable up to 3 week.

Key word: *Moringa oleifera* leaves, Mango squash, Antioxidant, Sensory analysis

Introduction

Moringa oleifera Lam. belonging to the family Moringaceae, it is an attractive plant, has native to South Asia and should grow in Himalayan foothills and also worldwide in tropics and sub – tropics. *Moringa oleifera* is well-known for its pod and leaves for use in delicious Indian cuisine. Economically *Moringa* plant is valuable, because it's all parts viz. roots, nuts, seeds, bark and flowers are edible in nature. *Moringa* seed oil can repels rancidity, has non-sticking characteristics, after extraction of oil remaining cake can be used for purification of drinking water. *Moringa* leaves are very good source of protein, Vitamin A, B & C and this nutrients are very much advantageous to pregnant women, nursing mother, infants and young kids also products from any part of *moringa* plant have antiulcer, antispasmodic, anti-trypanosomal, antibiotic, hypoglycemic, hypotensive, hypo-cholesterolemic and anti-inflammatory properties (FAO, 2020). Family of Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) is Anacardiaceae. Mango is also known as Aam, king of fruits and National fruit of India. Fresh and processed form of mango is being exported worldwide countries like Singapore, Malasiya U.S.A, U.K, U.A.E etc. with huge demand especially for Kesar and Alphanso variety. Mango is rich source of anti-dileutic, wound healing, immunomodulation, anti-lipid peroxidation, anti-degenerative, cardiotionic, hypotensive, and strong antioxidant properties. From ripe mango various value added products can be prepare like squash, jam, preserve, syrup, jelly, juice etc. Similar way un ripe mango can be convert in to chutney, pickles etc which is well accepted among consumer cause of their acidic taste. On the basis of analysis of more than 25 varieties of mango, it contains moisture 73.0-86.7 per cent, carbohydrate 11.6-24.3 per cent, protein 0.3-1.0 per cent, fat 0.1- 0.8 per cent, minerals 0.3-0.7 per cent, vitamin A 650-25940 I.U., vitamin C 3-83 mg/100g, calcium 0.01 per cent, phosphorus 0.02 per cent and iron 4.5 mg/100 g. (Mahendra Chaudhary *et al*, 2017).

Researchers have reported that complementary foods incorporating MLP either as part of a cereal–legume complementary food blend (blend of moringa leaves powder, cereals and legumes (MCL) -35 g contain maize 60%, soybean 25%, and moringa leaves powder 15%.) or when sprinkled as a food supplement (MS-5 g) on infant's usual foods were well accepted. (Laurene Boateng *et al*. 2018). Though this plant have numerous therapeutic value but because of lack of processing there are very few value added products are available in market prepared from various parts from *Moringa* and also MLP is power pack of nutrients but it is highly astringent in taste and

particularly unpleasant in its original form, so it can be added to meals and drinks to overcome its taste and Thus this research was aimed to find compatibilities of MLP with mango pulp in squash.

Material And Methods**Raw material**

The experiment was conducted in the laboratory of the Department of Food Technology. Good quality of mango pulp, drumstick leaves powder, sugar, ginger and jaljira collected from the market were used in the study, citric acid and other materials required were used from the laboratory stock

Formulations and Preparation of Functional squash

The basic formulations used for preparation of functional squash are outlined as on the basis of filler trial fixed quantity of mango pulp as 50 %, citric acid 0.5 %, ginger juice 01 %, jaljira 01 %, and optimize sugar level and MLP based on RSM trials as show in Table 1.1. Add remaining quantity of water for make up 100 ml. Functional squash was prepared as per flow diagram shown in Figure 1.1

Fig. 1.1 : Flow diagram of Preparation of Functional squash

Mango pulp mix it with MLP

Sugar, citric acid and boiled them in water till they dissolved

Cool down

Prepared syrup mix with mango pulp and MLP

Add ginger juice and jaljira as per recipe

Packaging

Physical, chemical, microbiological and sensory analysis**Physical property**

Optimized functional squash was tested for measure a viscosity using ostwald viscometer.

Chemical Properties

The acidity of functional squash was determined by the procedure given by A.O.A.C 17th edn., 2000, Official method 942.15 Acidity (Titrable) of fruit products read with A.O.A.C official method 920.149 Preparation of test sample. The pH of all samples was also

measured by using pH meter. Total soluble solids ($^{\circ}$ Brix) were estimated by using refractometer

Microbiological Properties

Determination of total plate count (TPC) and total yeast and mold count (TMC): For total viable count of bacteria and counting of total yeast and mold present in optimized squash were determined according to the method as described in the "Manual of methods of analysis of foods – Microbiological testing" (FSSAI, 2012).

Storage study

Optimized functional squash were stored at refrigeration temperature ($5\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) and ambient temperature ($26\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) for a period of 4 weeks and quality parameters were assessed. The samples were coded as S_1 (stored at refrigeration temperature, $5\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) & S_2 (stored at room temperature, $26\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$). Samples were examined at an interval of seven days during the storage period.

Statistical Analysis

All Data were analyzed using the software, design expert, version 11.0.3.0 and Completely Randomized Design. Final product was optimized based on data of sensory analysis obtained during storage study which contain a panel of 9 semi trained judges evaluated

Table 1.1 Optimization

Treatment No.	Factor 1	Factor 2	Mean sensory scores of organoleptic characteristics			
	Sugar (%)	Drumstick leaves powder (%)	Body and texture	Color and appearance	Flavor	Overall acceptability
1	20.00	0.83	3.8 ^c	4.2 ^{cd}	2.8 ^{cd}	3.8 ^c
2	25.00	0.65	7.8 ^a	7.4 ^a	6.4 ^a	7.2 ^a
3	27.07	0.83	2.8 ^{cd}	3.4 ^{de}	3.2 ^c	4.2 ^c
4	15.00	1.00	1.4 ^e	1.6 ^f	1.4 ^e	1.8 ^e
5	25.00	1.00	1.8 ^{de}	1.6 ^f	1.4 ^e	1.8 ^e
6	12.92	0.83	3.2 ^c	3.2 ^e	2.2 ^{de}	2.8 ^d
7	20.00	0.57	5.8 ^b	6.4 ^b	5.4 ^b	5.6 ^b
8	20.00	1.07	1.4 ^e	1.0 ^f	1.4 ^e	1.0 ^e
9	15.00	0.65	3.6 ^c	5.0 ^c	4.8 ^b	4.2 ^c
		SEm \pm	0.35	0.32	0.34	0.31
		CD @ 5%	1.01	0.95	0.98	0.85
		CV %	22.45	19.65	23.82	18.98

Mean with different superscripts within a Column are significantly different and the same superscripts are not significantly different (CD @ 5%)

Fig. 1.2: comparison with respect to organoleptic score

Fig. 1.3 : Optimized products Vs. Mango squash

Table 1.2 Results of Physical, Chemical and Microbiological analysis

Storage Period (week)	Mean sensory scores of organoleptic characteristics			
	Body & texture	Color & appearance	Flavor	Overall
1	7.6 ^a	7.8 ^a	7.2 ^a	7.4 ^a
2	7.4 ^a	7.4 ^a	7.2 ^a	7.0 ^a
3	7.0 ^a	7.4 ^a	7.2 ^a	7.0 ^a
4	6.8 ^a	7.2 ^{ab}	6.4 ^a	6.8 ^a
5	6.4 ^a	6.4 ^b	4 ^b	4.6 ^b
SEm ±	0.28	0.30	0.24	0.22
CD @ 5%	NS	0.90	0.70	0.67
CV %	9.21	9.37	8.22	7.77

A: Mango Squash with MLP B: Mango Squash without MLP

Optimized product were analyzed in a fresh form for physical, chemical and microbiological analysis, data of analysis are as per Table 1.2. It is also observed that there is very negligible variation in chemical properties (i.e. acidity and pH) and microbiological properties (TPC, Coliform count and TMC) during 28 days storage study.

Table 1.3 : Optimization of storage Study based on the sensory characteristics of functional squash For Sample S₁

Physical analysis	
Viscosity	570 cps
Chemical analysis	
Acidity (%)	1.23
pH	4.3
TSS (%)	42
Microbiological analysis	
TPC (cfu/ml)	80
Coliform count (cfu/ml)	Absent
TMC (cfu/ml)	18

The storage quality of processed functional squash (packed in sterilized glass bottle) were evaluated for different sensory attributes by a panel of 9 semi trained judges for the period of 4 weeks at ambient & refrigeration temperature. The samples were coded with letters and served to the panelists at random to guard against any bias. The storage quality evaluation was done for body and texture, color & appearance, flavor and overall acceptability in nine point hedonic scale. The score for color & appearance, flavor and overall acceptability of the functional squash are presented in Table 1.3. Flavor is a combination of various sensations derived from foods so from Table 1.3, it is found that for sample S₁, flavor was agreeable for the storage study from 1st week to 4th week and It is found that there is significance difference (CD at 5%) within a columns between mean scores of all sensory characteristics (except body and texture) from 1st week to 4th week and 5th week at refrigeration temperature,

Table 1.4: Nutritional analysis of mango squash with MLP

Sr. No.	Observations	Result
1.	Energy (kcal/100 g)	186.20
2.	Moisture (%)	53.16
3.	Total Ash (%)	0.89
4.	Viscosity (cps)	570.00
5.	Total Fat (g/100g)	0.48
6.	Protein (g/100g)	1.88
7.	Carbohydrate (g/100 g)	43.59
8.	Sugar (g/100 g)	34.51
9.	Calcium (mg/100 g)	156.85
10.	Sodium (mg/100 g)	210.06
11.	Iron (mg/100g)	1.82
12.	Vitamin C (mg/100g)	5.17

5±10⁰C and for sample S₂, significant difference (CD at 5%) within a columns between mean scores of all sensory characteristics (except body and texture) from 1st week to 3rd week and 4th week when stored at room temperature. On the other hand, taste and overall acceptability of the functional squash was well accepted till the fourth weeks and third weeks when stored at refrigeration temperature and room temperature respectively based on sensory analysis score. The acceptability of blended squash in terms of organoleptic score decreased gradually during the storage period at room temperature. Similar results on reduction in organoleptic quality have also been reported in kinnow, mandarin and ginger juice blended squash (Nidhi *et al.*, 2008), mango squash (Kumari and Sandal, 2011) Karonda squash (Deen and Singh, 2012).

Optimized squash with MLP, in a fresh form tested for nutritional analysis, results are shown in Table 1.4.

For Sample S₂

Storage Period (week)	Mean sensory scores of organoleptic characteristics			
	Body & texture	Color & appearance	Flavor	Overall acceptability
1	7.6 ^a	7.8 ^a	7.0 ^a	7.2 ^a
2	7.4 ^a	7.4 ^a	6.6 ^a	6.8 ^a
3	7.0 ^a	7.4 ^a	6.4 ^a	6.8 ^a
4	6.6 ^a	5.8 ^b	3.6 ^b	4.2 ^b
	SEm ±	0.26	0.27	0.38
	CD @ 5%	NS	0.82	1.14
	CV %	8.23	8.63	14.43

Mean with different superscripts within a columns are significantly different and the same superscripts not significantly different (CD @ 5%)

Conclusion

During the optimization of level of *Moringa oleifera*'s leaves powder it was found that beyond 0.65% quantity squash get dark green color and it was not accepted in sensory analysis so it is advised to prepare functional squash by using optimized recipe: quantity of mango pulp 50 %, citric acid 0.5 %, ginger juice 1 %, jaljira 1 %, sugar 25 % & drumstick leaves powder 0.65 %. Functional squash is rich in calcium, sodium and Iron which is good for women and children for their healthy growth. Plant of drumstick (*Moringa oleifera*) is under-utilized and easy available so it is advisable to used its leaves powder for making squash. Squash could be stored up to 4 week concern with quality and overall acceptance at refrigeration temperature while for same acceptable up to 3 week at room temperature.

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